

LOCAL DERIVATIONS OF METABELIAN FILIFORM LIE ALGEBRAS

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Introduction

Let A be an algebra (not necessary associative). Recall that a linear mapping $D: A \rightarrow A$ is said to be a derivation, if $D(xy) = D(x)y + xD(y)$ for all $x, y \in A$. A linear mapping Δ is said to be a local derivation, if for every $x \in A$ there exists a derivation D_x on A (depending on x) such that $\Delta(x) = D_x(x)$.

This notion was introduced and investigated independently by R.V. Kadison [11] and D.R. Larson and A.R. Sourour [12]. The above papers gave rise to a series of works devoted to the description of mappings which are close to automorphisms and derivations of C^* -algebras and operator algebras. R.V. Kadison set out a program of study for local maps in [11], suggesting that local derivations could prove useful in building derivations with particular properties. R.V. Kadison proved in [11, Theorem A] that each continuous local derivation of a von Neumann algebra M into a dual Banach M -bimodule is a derivation. This theorem gave way to studies on derivations on C^* -algebras, culminating with a result due to B.E. Johnson, which asserts that every local derivation of a C^* -algebra A into a Banach A -bimodule is automatically continuous, and hence is a derivation [7, Theorem 5.3].

Let us present a list of finite or infinite dimensional algebras for which all local derivations are derivations:

- C^* -algebras, in particular, the algebra $M_n(\mathbb{C})$ of all square matrices of order n over the field of complex numbers [7, 11];
- the complex polynomial algebra $\mathbb{C}[x]$ [11];
- finite dimensional simple Lie algebras over an algebraically closed field of characteristic zero [3];
- Borel subalgebras of finite-dimensional simple Lie algebras [18];
- infinite dimensional Witt algebras over an algebraically closed field of characteristic zero [5];
- Witt algebras over a field of prime characteristic [19];
- solvable Lie algebras of maximal rank [13].

On the other hand, some algebras (in most cases close to nilpotent algebras) admit pure local derivations, that is, local derivations which are not derivations. Below a short list of some classes of algebras which admit pure local derivations:

- the algebra $C(x)$ of rational functions [11];
- finite dimensional filiform Lie algebras [3];
- solvable Leibniz algebras with abelian nilradicals, which have a one dimensional complementary space [2];
- the algebra of lower triangular $n \times n$ -matrices [6];
- real octonion algebra [4].

2. Local derivations of metabelian filiform Lie algebras

In this subsection we obtain a description of the space of all local derivations of rank zero solvable Lie algebras with filiform nilradical, namely with a so-called metabelian filiform Lie radical.

A non-abelian Lie algebra L is called a metabelian, if $[L, L]$ is abelian, that is, $L^{(2)} = 0$.

We shall consider a metabelian filiform Lie algebra L of dimension $n \geq 7$ with a basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} [e_1, e_i] &= e_{i+1}, & 2 \leq i \leq n-1, [e_2, e_i] &= e_{i+2} + e_{i+3}, \\ 3 \leq i \leq n-3, [e_2, e_{n-2}] &= e_n. \end{aligned}$$

By [16, Proposition 3.2.5], any derivation D on L has the strictly lower triangular matrix $(d_{i,j})$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{2,1} &= 0, \\ d_{i+1,i} &= d_{3,2}, & 3 \leq i < n; \\ d_{ij} &= d_{i-j+2,2} - d_{i-j+1,1} - d_{i-j,1} & 3 \leq j < i-1 < n. \end{aligned}$$

Note that the numbers $d_{i,j}$ ($3 \leq i, j \leq n$) completely determined by $d_{k,1}, d_{k,2}$ ($k = 3, \dots, n$) and the space of all derivations $\text{Der}(L)$ has the dimension $2n - 4$.

Theorem. *A linear mapping Δ on L is a local derivation if and only if it has a strictly lower triangular matrix $(\delta_{i,j})$ with $\delta_{2,1} = 0$.*

Proof. It is clear that any local derivation Δ on L has a strictly lower triangular matrix $(\delta_{i,j})$ with $\delta_{2,1} = 0$.

Let Δ be a such matrix. Take an arbitrary element $x = \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i e_i$. Let

$$\Delta(x) = \sum_{i=3}^n \zeta_i e_i. \text{ We need to find a derivation } D_x \text{ such that } \Delta(x) = D_x(x).$$

We shall consider the following possible two cases.

Case 1. Let $\xi_1 \neq 0$. Take

$$\begin{aligned} d_{3,1} &= \frac{\zeta_3}{\xi_1}, \\ d_{4,1} &= \frac{\zeta_4}{\xi_1}, \\ d_{i,2} &= 0, \quad i = 3, \dots, n. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Further, for $i = 5, \dots, n$ the numbers $d_{i,1}$ define as follows:

$$d_{i,1} = \frac{1}{\xi_1} \left(\zeta_i - \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j \right), \tag{2}$$

where $d_{ij} = -d_{i-j+1,1} - d_{i-j,1}, 3 \leq j < i-1 < n$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} D_x(x) &= \sum_{i=3}^n \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i = d_{3,1} \xi_1 e_3 + d_{4,1} \xi_1 e_4 + \sum_{i=5}^n d_{i,1} \xi_1 e_i + \sum_{i=5}^n \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i \\ &\stackrel{(1),(2)}{=} \zeta_3 e_3 + \zeta_4 e_4 + \sum_{i=5}^n \zeta_i e_i - \sum_{i=5}^n \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i + \sum_{i=5}^n \sum_{j=3}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i \\ &= \sum_{i=3}^n \zeta_i e_i = \Delta(x). \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. Let $\xi_1 = \dots = \xi_{s-1} = 0, \xi_s \neq 0$, where $2 \leq s \leq n-1$. Then $\Delta(x) = \sum_{i=s+1}^n \zeta_i e_i$.

Set

$$\begin{aligned} d_{i,1} &= 0, \quad i = 3, \dots, n, \\ d_{3,2} = d_{i+1,i} &= \frac{\zeta_{s+1}}{\xi_s}, \quad i = 3, \dots, n-1 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and

$$d_{i-s+2,2} = \frac{1}{\xi_s} \left(\zeta_i - \sum_{j=s+1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j \right), \quad i = s+2, \dots, n,$$

$$d_{i-s+2,2} = 0, \quad i = n+1, \dots, n+s-2, \quad (4)$$

where

$$d_{ij} = d_{i-j+2,2}, 3 \leq j < i-1 < n. \quad (5)$$

Then

$$D_x(x) = \sum_{i=3}^n \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i = \sum_{i=s+1}^n \sum_{j=s}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i$$

$$= d_{s+1,s} \xi_s e_{s+1} + \sum_{i=s+2}^n d_{i,s} \xi_s e_i + \sum_{i=s+2}^n \sum_{j=s+1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i$$

$$\stackrel{(5)}{=} d_{s+1,s} \xi_s e_{s+1} + \sum_{i=s+2}^n d_{i-s+2,2} \xi_s e_i + \sum_{i=s+2}^n \sum_{j=s+1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i$$

$$\stackrel{(5)(3),(5)(3)(4)}{=} \zeta_{s+1} e_{s+1} + \sum_{i=s+2}^n \zeta_i e_i - \sum_{i=s+2}^n \sum_{j=s+1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i + \sum_{i=s+2}^n \sum_{j=s+1}^{i-1} d_{i,j} \xi_j e_i$$

$$= \sum_{i=s+1}^n \zeta_i e_i = \Delta(x).$$

The proof is complete.

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